

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING REFLEXIVE SKILLS USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада бошланғич синф ўқувчиларида ўйин технологияси асосида ўз-ўзини билиш ҳамда баҳолашга қаратилган рефлексив кўникмаларни шакллантириш методлари ҳақида сўз боради.

Калит сўзлар

Ўйин, метод, жараён, восита, феномен, психолог, педагог, самарадорлик.

Аннотация

В данной статье идет речь о методах формирования рефлексивных умений и навыков у младших школьников на основе игровой технологии, направленной на самопознание и оценку.

Ключевые слова

игра, метод, процесс, средство, явление, психолог, педагог, результативность.

Abstract

this article will focus on the methods of formation of reflexive skills and abilities in younger schoolchildren based on game technology aimed at self-knowledge and evaluation.

Keywords

game, method, process, means, phenomenon, psychologist, teacher, effectiveness.

It is not a secret to all of us that issues of fundamental reform of education and upbringing, science and vocational training systems have been successfully implemented throughout the country, and high efficiency is being achieved in the field of education. In this, together with the teachers, the general public, acknowledging the selfless work of our entire nation, President Sh. The success of large-scale reforms implemented in all areas based on the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan M. Mirziyoev dated October 29, 2020 "On approval of the concept of development of science until 2030" No. He emphasized that it is related to the development of science and education.

This great sense of responsibility requires teachers to improve various processes of pedagogical skills at the level of modern requirements. In recent years,

pedagogues and psychologists have emphasized that the development of thinking and analytical skills is of great importance in the pedagogical activity of teachers. The basis of these abilities is the teacher's professional reflection.

Reflection (lat. «reflexio»-to return) is a form of theoretical activity aimed at understanding one's own actions and their laws; It is an activity aimed at self-knowledge and understanding, which reveals the unique hidden features of the human spiritual world. For the first time, the concept of reflection arose in ancient Greek philosophy and is the process of a person thinking about the thoughts that are going on in his mind. It meant drawing attention to the analysis of the content of one's thoughts (Descartes). Socrates, Plato, Locke and other Greek philosophers emphasize that reflection is the activity of a person aimed at self-knowledge and recognition of what he is capable of.¹⁸.

Our goal is to develop methods of forming reflexive skills aimed at self-knowledge and evaluation in elementary school students based on game technology. Therefore, if we consider the importance and tasks of game technologies, the method of games allows students of junior school age to make a gradual transition from game activities that are customary for them to educational activities, which helps to pass the transition process imperceptibly and without any difficulties. It is necessary for each teacher to understand the purpose of each game, its content, to organize the game taking into account the specific tasks of mastering the subject for each lesson, and to think of a method of forming reflexive skills in students. Because the game is one of the main types of human activity, like work and education, and it is a strange phenomenon of our existence. In human life, game activity performs the following functions:

entertainment to distract from everyday tasks (function of making fun, arousing interest, inspiration);

communicativeness: mastering the dialectic of communication;

showing itself in the game as a training ground for human practice;

play therapy: overcoming various obstacles that appear during life activities;

diagnostic: self-awareness during the game, detection of deviation from normal behavior;

performing the correction function: making positive changes in the composition of personal indicators;

international communications: mastering social values that are common to all

¹⁸ Декарт Р. *Сочинения*, тт. 1–2. М., 1989–1991 г

people;

- socialization: inclusion in the system of social relations, assimilation of the general norms of human existence. As

an activity, the game includes integrated planning, goal realization, and analysis of its results in the self-identification of a person as a subject. The motive of game activity is provided by its voluntariness, choice and competitive elements, satisfying the need for self-expression.

The game has been used since ancient times as a method of education, in order to pass on the experiences of the older generation to the younger generation. The widespread use of games can be observed in public pedagogy and in non-school institutions. From game activities in modern general secondary schools: - as independent technologies for mastering the concept, topic and some sections of the educational subject; - as an element of relatively large-scale technologies;

- as a training (lesson) or part of it (introduction, explanation, reinforcement, exercises, control);

- used as a technology for extracurricular activities (for example, traffic lights, jump starts, etc.). The

concept of game technologies includes sufficiently wide methods and ways of organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games. First of all, it should not be overlooked that the game is a means of communication in education and a complex socio-cultural phenomenon for gathering life experience. Psychologists and pedagogues have identified the development of the ability to imagine and figurative thinking in the game. The student will have the ability to use life images during the game, which in turn will serve as a basis for moving on to the next complex creative activity. In addition, the importance of the development of imagination is self-evident, because without it, even the simplest human activity is impossible. The game also has a great impact on the development of students' relationships with their peers. In addition, during the game, he learns the rules while performing interactions and actions, and as a result of recalling and repeating his knowledge, he gets the experience of mutual understanding. We all know how necessary such qualities are during the later life of a student, first of all at school, where the student has to join a large group of peers, pay attention to the teacher's explanations in the classroom, control his actions in completing homework assignments.

The role of the game in the acquisition of knowledge and its duration depend on many factors, these factors depend on the following: the level of education of the students, the level of ability to absorb information, the level of complexity of the material to be mastered or the

control of the material coming from other languages, and the orientation of the training session to specific goals. Here are some examples of methods that help build these reflexive skills:

"Study of the classification process" methodology

Purpose: the sequence of reasoning is applied to research the level of generalization processes.

Preparation for methodology. We will select 5 pictures of 7x7cm size for each classification group: toys, dishes, clothes, furniture, wild animals, domestic animals, vegetables, fruits.

Transfer of methodology. The game is played individually with each student. The student is given one picture and asked: "Sort the pictures according to their compatibility with each other. Explain why they fit together." If the student participating in the game is doing the division without any explanation, ask him: "Why did you put a picture of an apple in this part? Why do you think that an apple is a fruit?" questions like If the student cannot place a picture into any of the groups, then ask him, "Why do you think this picture does not fit into any of the groups?" is asked. For example: Pineapple

Data processing. Correct answers are listed by group in each classification. The result is displayed in the table. In order to combine the subjects, the basis is determined according to the group of students in each classification: did they rely on the important sign, were they able to distinguish the non-important ones? and so on.

"Understanding metaphors" methodology

Purpose: orientation of thinking towards the goal, ability to understand and use the content of the educational text, classification of opinions and orientation towards the goal, their depth, level of development of speech processes.

Preparation for conducting the methodology. A number of proverbs and metaphors should be chosen and the reader should explain their meaning. **Transfer of methodology.** The methodology is conducted individually with each student. The teacher reads a proverb or a metaphor and asks: "What do these words mean, what do you understand?". For example: What does "open mind" mean? **Data processing.** The reader's ability to explain the meaning of the proposed metaphor, as well as their understanding of the figurative meaning, is analyzed.

"Sequential Pictures"

Purpose: to develop the ability to connect coherently, to understand the sequence of events.

Preparation for conducting the methodology. A sequence of plot pictures (from 3 to 6) is selected, depicting some event stages. The pictures should be appropriate for the age of the students, clearly described, and noticeable.

Implementation of the methodology. The methodology is conducted individually with each student. A student is shown a random mix of pictures and asked: "These pictures depict one event. Analyze where it started, what it continued with, and how it ended. Put the first image here (showing its location), i.e. the starting image, here-the second one, ..., here-the last one". After the student arranges the pictures, the arrangement of the pictures is recorded and the student is asked to describe what the arrangement produces. If the student has placed the pictures in the wrong order, he will be asked questions in order to determine the contradiction in his reasoning, the mistakes made. If the questions do not help to understand the depicted phenomena, then the teacher of the method shows the student the first picture and offers to place the rest. Thus, the second attempt to complete the task is executed. If that doesn't help either, then the reader is shown and told the sequence of events. Then the pictures are shuffled again and the student is asked to place them. If the student places the pictures in the correct order after the third time, he is given another picture sequence (of similar complexity, to determine whether he can transfer his reasoning to the new situation). If the student can complete the task from the first time, he will be offered a new sequence of pictures, more complicated than the previous one. Data processing. Whether the student can establish cause-and-effect relationships from the sequence of visually presented pictures, whether he understands the sequence of events is analyzed.

Exercise "Main Character".

Children are invited to choose a sign-word from ten words written on the board.

Teacher:

ten different words are written on the board. Read them and choose the symbol-word that matches each one. The sign-word determines the property of the subject and how? - answers the question. For example, sand can be yellow, hot, fine, etc. Choose the symbol-word that you think is closest and write it under the line. Writing in the notebook is carried out in the following order: pairs of words are written in decimal form - the words suggested by the teacher are on top, and the words are suggested by the student on the bottom. The teacher discusses one example. Students complete the task. Then the words written by the students are discussed. Together with the class, it is discussed whether the symbols are chosen correctly or not. The teacher gives the students the task of remembering these words and the selected symbols. In the next lesson, the teacher asks them to

remember the words in pairs and the symbols chosen for them, to write them in a notebook, and then to compare and repeat the notes they wrote in the previous lesson.

We can conclude that the game is an educational tool that activates the mental abilities of learners, makes the learning process interesting and exciting, and motivates students to learn self-analysis.

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